

Evaluation of Pattern of Injury in Terms of Severity and Outcome in Patients with Head Injuries Admitted in Trauma UnitSandeep Yadav¹, Madhu Priya²¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of study to know the pattern of injury in terms of severity and outcome in patients with head injuries admitted in trauma unit of a tertiary care Centre in Bihar region.**Methods:** This study included 200 patients admitted Department of General Surgery. Thereafter a complete history of all patients of head injury sustained due to RTA or fall was taken after taking written & informed consent. Those with poly trauma and others not attending the OPD for check-ups timely were eliminated from study. After admission in head injury unit, physical examination was performed in all subjects.**Results:** It was observed that incidence of head injury was more in males than the females. Out of 200 cases, 175 (87.5%) victims were males and 25 (12.5%) cases were females. Out of 200 cases, maximum incidence of head injury was found in the age group of 21-30 years comprising 50 (25%) cases, followed by 31-40 years 46 (23%) and 41-50 years 40 (20%). The age group 51-60 yrs comprised of 34 (17%) cases. The other affected groups were 61-70 years and 71-80 years group comprising of 12 (6%) cases and 8 (4%) cases respectively. It was observed that road traffic accident was the commonest cause of head injury seen in 144 (72%) cases. This was followed by fall from height 32 (16%) cases and assault 20 (10%) cases. The other causes like fall of tree or wall over-head were seen in 2% cases. It was seen that most of the cases 122 (61%) died within 24 hours of admission to the hospital. 28 (14%) cases survived for 1-2 days. 20 (10%) of cases survived for 2-3 days. 20 (10%) cases survived for 3-7 days and about 10 (5%) of cases survived for more than 7 days. Thus the most fatal period was first 24 hours. Out of 200 cases, 15 cases expired.**Conclusion:** The study showed that most head injury victims brought to a tertiary care hospital, were due to road traffic accidents and males are more prone to get Head injury. So it warrants the urgency to establish good pre-hospital care and provision of efficient and prompt trauma services at Road side to prevent mortality aroused from RTA. RTA remains the most common cause for Head injury and demands good neurosurgical care for such patients.**Keywords:** Head injury, Skull fracture, Intracranial haemorrhage

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Introduction

The incidence of head injury is growing with greater mechanization in industry and an increase in high-velocity transport. The injuries could be caused by a penetrating or blunt force either by direct violence or indirectly, such as a fall at the feet or buttocks. There is no clear relation to the severity of injury to skull bones and the extent of cerebral disorder. Head Injury has been defined as, morbid state, resulting from gross or subtle structural changes in the scalp, skull, and/ or the contents of the skull, produced by mechanical forces. [1] It has also been defined as physical damage to the scalp, skull or brain produced by an external force. [2] However, such force or impact, responsible for the injury, needs not to be applied directly to the head.

Depending upon whether the dura-matter was torn or not, head injury may be termed as open or close type. [3] The extent and degree of injury to the skull and its contents is not necessarily proportional to the quantum of force applied to the head. According to Munro [4] "any type of craniocerebral injury can be caused by any kind of blow on any sort of head." Severe head injury, with or without peripheral trauma, is the commonest cause of death and/or disability up to the age of 45 years in developed countries. [5] This necessitated an in-depth analysis on the pattern of head Injury in road traffic accidents and other factors influencing the Pattern of head injuries.

Any change in mental or physical performance associated with a blow on the head, associated with or without altered level of consciousness is defined as head injury [6], may be mild to severe depending on the impact & duration of injury. In the developing and developed nations the commonest reason of mortality and morbidity are injuries related to RTA (Road traffic accidents) and this may also consequence in short term or long term disability. [7] Therefore may act as a socioeconomic burden on such countries. Globally, injuries related to RTA are the most important reasons for disability adjusted life years lost and ranked at ninth level, and this is predicted to rank to third by 2020. [8]

Head injury is a major public health problem and has already attained epidemic proportions in India. As a result craniocerebral trauma places a huge financial and psychological burden upon the society. In India, the problem has become more acute over the last two decades, mainly due to increased vehicular traffic and poor maintenance on the road. The aim of study to know the pattern of injury in terms of severity and outcome in patients with head injuries admitted in trauma unit of a tertiary care Centre in Bihar region.

Materials and Methods

This study included 200 patients admitted Department of General Surgery, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India for 12 months. Thereafter a complete history of all patients of head injury sustained due to RTA or fall was taken after taking written & informed consent. Those with poly trauma and others not attending the OPD for check-ups timely were eliminated from study. After admission in head injury unit, physical examination was performed in all subjects.

In needy subjects resuscitation measures were done before referring the subjects for CT scan brain.

Patients were divided into severe (GCS 3-8), moderate (GCS 9-13) and mild head injury (GCS 14-15) based on GCS level. CT scan brain with bone window was done for all patients to confirm their diagnosis. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) was used for categorizing the subjects with head injury into mild (GCS 14-15), moderate (GCS 9-13) and severe injury (GCS 3-8). All subjects went for CT scan brain with bone window for confirmation of diagnosis.

The outcomes at follow up of patients after traumatic head injury were observed through Glasgow outcome scale. The outcomes observed were categorized as; 1. Death, 2. Persistent vegetative state (minimum responsiveness), 3. Severe disability (subject is conscious, disabled and dependent), 4. Moderate disability: subject is disabled but independent (can work in sheltered settings) and 5. Good recovery: minor deficits with resumption of normal life.

A printed proforma was used to collect the data and this included the biodata of subjects as name, age, gender, manner of trauma, neurological condition at arrival, type and outcome of treatment. The subjects and/or their relatives were explained about disease prognosis and the requirement of any type of medical or surgical treatment during the course of management. For the avoidance of bias or confusing issues, exclusion criteria were followed strictly.

Regarding statistical Analysis; data was entered and analyzed in statistical software (SPSS-20). Frequency and percentages were computed for categorical variables like age groups, gender, diagnosis, GCS, and surgical outcome including Glasgow outcome scale. Mean and standard deviation confidence interval were computed for quantitative measurement like age.

Results

Table 1: Age & Sex wise distribution of Head injury cases

Age in years	No. of cases		Total	%
	Males	Females		
0-10	00	00	00	00
11-20	10	00	10	5
21-30	40	10	50	25
31-40	46	00	46	23
41-50	34	6	40	20
51-60	30	4	34	17
61-70	9	3	12	6
71-80	6	2	8	4
>81	00	00	00	00
TOTAL	175	25	200	100

It was observed that incidence of head injury was more in males than the females. Out of 200 cases, 175 (87.5%) victims were males and 25 (12.5%) cases were females. Out of 200 cases, maximum incidence of head injury was found in the age group of 21-30 years comprising 50 (25%) cases, followed

by 31-40 years 46 (23%) and 41-50 years 40 (20%). The age group 51-60 yrs comprised of 34 (17%) cases. The other affected groups were 61-70 years and 71-80 years group comprising of 12 (6%) cases and 8 (4%) cases respectively.

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to cause of head injury and according to survival time

Cause of Head Injury	No. of Cases	%
Road traffic accident	144	72
Fall from height	32	16
Assault	20	10
Others	4	2
Survival period		
Within 24 hours	122	61
1-2 days	28	14
2-3 days	20	10
3 – 7 days	20	10
> 7 days	10	5

It was observed that road traffic accident was the commonest cause of head injury seen in 144 (72%) cases. This was followed by fall from height 32 (16%) cases and assault 20 (10%) cases. The other causes like fall of tree or wall over-head were seen in 2% cases. It was seen that most of the cases 122

(61%) died within 24 hours of admission to the hospital. 28 (14%) cases survived for 1-2 days. 20 (10%) of cases survived for 2-3 days. 20 (10%) cases survived for 3-7 days and about 10 (5%) of cases survived for more than 7 days. Thus the most fatal period was first 24 hours.

Table 3: Distribution of cases according to type of skull fracture

Type of skull fracture	No. of cases	%
Linear (Fissured)	82	41
Depressed	28	14
Comminuted	20	10
No fracture	70	35

It was evident that linear fracture was observed in 82 (41%) cases followed by depressed fracture in 28 (14%) and comminuted fracture in 20 (10%) cases. Thus the linear fracture was the most common skull fracture encountered at autopsy examination.

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to location skull fracture

Location of skull fracture		No of cases	%
Cranial Vault	Temporal	82	41
	Parietal	40	20
	Frontal	16	8
	Occipital	10	5
Base of skull	Anterior Cranial Fossa	20	10
	Middle Cranial Fossa	16	8
	Posterior Cranial Fossa	16	8

It was seen that temporal bone was involved in skull fracture accounting for 82 (41%) cases followed by parietal bone 40 (20%) cases, frontal bone 16 (8%) and occipital bone 10 (5%) cases. Thus temporal bone was the most common bone involved in

fracture of skull in the present study. Regarding the base of skull, anterior cranial fossa is involved in 20 (10%) cases followed by middle cranial fossa in 16 (8%) cases and posterior cranial fossa in 16 (8%) cases.

Table 5: Distribution of cases according to type of intracranial hemorrhage and brain injury

Type of Intracranial Hemorrhage and brain injury	No. of cases	%
SDH	166	83
SAH	160	80
EDH	40	20
ICH	20	10
IVH	10	5
Contusion	96	48
Laceration	46	23
Cerebral edema	70	35

It was observed that subdural haemorrhage was the most common type of haemorrhage detected in 166 (83%) cases closely followed by subarachnoid haemorrhage (SAH) in 160 (80%) cases, extradural haemorrhage (EDH) in 40 (20%) cases, intracerebral haemorrhage (ICH) in 20 (10%) cases and intraventricular Haemorrhage (IVH) in 10 (5%) cases.

Table 6: Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) Score

GCS score	No. of patients	Improved	Expired
15	170	170	-
13-14	12	10	2
8-12	10	5	5
< 8	8	-	8
Total	200	185	15

Out of 200 cases, 15 cases expired.

Discussion

Head injury is a significant public health problem worldwide and is predicted to surpass many diseases as a major cause of death by 2020. There is some data to indicate that majority of traumatic brain injury cases (60%) are as a result of road traffic accident, followed by falls (20-30%), and violence (10%). [9] Traumatic head injury is a leading cause of death and disability in children and adults in their most productive years. The morbidity and mortality due to head injury is on the rise and is one of the prime importance in today's medical practice. [10] Craniocerebral injury or Head injury is defined by National Advisory Neurological Diseases and Stroke Council as "a morbid state, resulting from gross or subtle structural changes in scalp, skull, and/ or the contents of the skull, produced by mechanical forces". Here, the forces are restricted to those that are applied externally to the head, thus excluding the surgical ablations and internally acting forces such as increased intracranial pressure resulting from oedema, hydrocephalus and mass occupying lesions without any antecedent trauma to the head. [11]

It was observed that incidence of head injury was more in males than the females. Out of 200 cases, 175 (87.5%) victims were males and 25 (12.5%) cases were females. Out of 200 cases, maximum incidence of head injury was found in the age group of 21-30 years comprising 50 (25%) cases, followed by 31-40 years 46 (23%) and 41-50 years 40 (20%). The age group 51-60 yrs comprised of 34 (17%) cases. The other affected groups were 61-70 years and 71-80 years group comprising of 12 (6%) cases and 8 (4%) cases respectively. Our findings are consistent with the study done by the other authors. [12-16] This age group (21-40 years) is the most vulnerable group involved in head injury cases. The obvious reason was that they are the main working group. This age group is most active phase of life physically and socially. People in this age group are constantly mobile for work, education or recreational activities. Hence prone to road traffic

accident, falls, assaults which are one of the major causes of head injuries.

It was observed that road traffic accident was the commonest cause of head injury seen in 144 (72%) cases. This was followed by fall from height 32 (16%) cases and assault 20 (10%) cases. The other causes like fall of tree or wall over-head were seen in 2% cases. Similar observation was made in studies done by other authors. [17,18] The other causes like fall of tree or wall over-head were seen in 2% cases. A common perception is that a large number of subjects injured in accidents especially motor vehicle, with TBI are young adult males. Although the majority of such injuries are related to motor vehicle accidents, but the type of injuries across various areas are different. It is observed that in developed nations motor vehicle owners usually present with TBI, on the other hand in middle or low socio-economic nations subjects with TBI are usually due to the road traffic users motorcyclist, cyclist and pedestrians. This rising frequency of TBI subjects in middle or low socio-economic nations could be due to increasing motorization, insufficient traffic related knowledge and slow accomplishment of traffic safety rules. [19]

It was seen that most of the cases 122 (61%) died within 24 hours of admission to the hospital. 28 (14%) cases survived for 1-2 days. 20 (10%) of cases survived for 2-3 days. 20 (10%) cases survived for 3-7 days and about 10 (5%) of cases survived for more than 7 days. Thus the most fatal period was first 24 hours. It was seen that temporal bone was involved in skull fracture accounting for 82 (41%) cases followed by parietal bone 40 (20%) cases, frontal bone 16 (8%) and occipital bone 10 (5%) cases. Thus temporal bone was the most common bone involved in fracture of skull in the present study. Regarding the base of skull, anterior cranial fossa is involved in 20 (10%) cases followed by middle cranial fossa in 16 (8%) cases and posterior cranial fossa in 16 (8%) cases. It was observed that subdural haemorrhage was the most common type of haemorrhage detected in 166 (83%) cases closely followed by subarachnoid haemorrhage (SAH) in 160 (80%) cases, extradural haemorrhage (EDH) in 40 (20%) cases, intracerebral haemorrhage (ICH) in

20 (10%) cases and intraventricular Haemorrhage (IVH) in 10 (5%) cases. In critical care medicine it is a main challenging issue of management in subjects with an score between 3 to 8 with severe brain injury related to trauma, and in the past two decades there is has been much improvement in managing the subjects with severe head injury. [20] The acute management, throughout the “GOLDEN HOUR”, i.e. duration from the time of injury to the initiation of decisive care which includes the strict ICU monitoring, should be in accordance with Head injury trauma guidelines. [21] Majority of patients admitted in our unit were with moderate to severe head injury. There is a solid relationship between the severity of injury and the results as noted by studies. Therefore, extreme safety measures should be taken which also includes treatment given at site of operation along with immediate transport of such patients to trauma units in ambulances well equipped to deal with such casualties. There is higher risk of post injury longstanding impairment of everyday tasks in children who have severe brain injury due to trauma especially in early child hood. [22] There is also a higher risk of longstanding impairment of routine work several years post injury especially in families who are coping poorly. [23]

Conclusion

The study showed that most head injury victims brought to hospital, were due to road traffic accidents and males are more prone to get Head injury. So it warrants the urgency to establish good pre-hospital care and provision of efficient and prompt trauma services at Road side to prevent mortality aroused from RTA. RTA remains the most common cause for Head injury and demands good neurosurgical care for such patients. By the compiling the records of these traumas at national level or international level can underline risk factors involved in these accidents, will be extremely helpful in the policy building and making the decisions for health promotion and health building at national or international level. This study thus proved that Good outcome is observed in patients who are properly treated by continuous monitoring & timely surgical intervention if required in a hospital. By improving outcome in such patients with head injuries we will decrease socioeconomic burden on developing country like ours.

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